

Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh

Faculty of Education and Social Sciences, University of Selangor, Malaysia
Email: abu_sheik@unisel.edu.my Tel. No: 60172023798

Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor

Faculty of Education and Social Sciences, University of Selangor, Malaysia
Email: nothman@unisel.edu.my Tel. No: 601165561603

Funding Information: Selangor State Government, Malaysia, 2021 (MYR10,000)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7573735>

Abstract

This study identified innovative teaching skills practices and constraints on innovative teaching among state government secondary school teachers. It is to overcome the issue of teachers who cannot interest students in subjects and teacher issues who cannot take advantage of the potential of students in creativity and issue solving. The study used a Qualitative Method design in which researchers collected and analysed non-numerical data such as transcripts or interview text to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. In this research, researchers used Phenomenological Research to investigate two types of phenomena, namely the phenomenon of innovative teaching skills practice and the phenomenon of innovative teaching constraints, by describing and interpreting the life experiences of study participants. A total of 25 study participants responded to Structured Interview Questions About Innovative Teaching Skills Practice and Structured Interview Questions About Innovative Teaching Constraints for qualitative studies. Researchers conducted a 16-week study. Researchers analysed qualitative data using *N vivo Version 11* software. This study found that teachers use innovative teaching strategies through computer technology-based teaching and collaborative groups. The findings also showed that teachers use innovative teaching strategies through question-based and problem-solving teaching. In addition, teachers face limitations in terms of time, task load, teaching aids, teaching aids, class sizes, and constraints in terms of lack of knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching. It also has implications for the practice of teachers, trainee teachers, new teachers, experienced teachers, expert teachers, and lecturers.

Keywords: Innovative teaching, innovative teaching constraints, practices, skills

Introduction

In the context of Education in this century, guidance and guidance on innovative use in teaching to teachers is important because it has diverse implications. The implication for students is that innovative has an impact on the effectiveness of student learning. Innovative also affect learning satisfaction. While the implication for teachers is that innovative improves the quality of teaching and the effectiveness of teachers. What is most significant is that this area of creativity and innovative studies meets the needs of the body of knowledge of the educational field of the educational component of specialization for secondary education.

In this regard, according to Lund and Gram (2017), education is a process that impacts students' attitudes, understanding, and belief systems. It further influences the actions of students. Thus, the educational process plays a meaningful role because it can be decisive so that the student becomes a citizen who can think for himself and boldly do different things. Students can also think and act out of the box to express ideas. In this sense, education is also related to self-creation that includes cognitive aspects, namely knowledge, understanding, beliefs, and actions.

Thus, this research article aims to explain innovative teaching skills practices among state government high school teachers. Finally, it aims to elaborate the constraints of innovative teaching among state government secondary school teachers. The rationale is, innovative teaching encourages teachers and students to explore, research, and use all the tools to reveal something new. It also helps students develop creativity and problem-solving skills.

This section deals with the statement of the problem of the study. As we have seen, several previous studies have stated that this issue is of interest and benefit to students and teachers. Literature review explore most of that research. Ideally, there is a growing sentiment among teachers that teachers can teach innovatively for students to develop students' ability to analyse and make independent assessments, as well as teachers can also stimulate student interest and motivate learning.

In fact, that, there is an important issue faced by teachers, which is that teachers cannot draw students' attention to learning in the classroom. According to Karen (2016), one issue is that teachers cannot interest students in subjects. Moreover, the teacher cannot make the student want to know more about the lesson. Further, the teacher cannot stimulate the minds of students and the teacher cannot make the student understand the subject. In addition, Kathryn (2016) says that there is an issue of teachers not mastering the core competencies of professional teachers.

As a result, the teacher also cannot take advantage of the potential of the student in creativity and the solution of issues, as well as the teacher cannot improve the learning ability of students (Guerriero & Révai, 2017). Based on the findings of Karen (2016), Kathryn (2016), and Guerriero & Révai (2017), it is clear that there are issues in terms of innovative teaching practices among teachers and constraints on innovative teaching among teachers. Because of this, researchers intend to study it in this research.

The purpose of this section is to highlight the objectives of this study. We conducted the study for the following objectives: (1) To explain innovative teaching skills practice among state

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

government secondary school teachers, (2) To elaborate the constraints of innovative teaching among state government secondary school teachers.

The meaning of this section is to ask this study question. Researchers conducted research to answer the following questions: (1) How is the innovative teaching skills practice among state government secondary school teachers? (2) How is the constraint of innovative teaching among state government secondary school teachers?

This section aims to elaborate on the limitations of this study. We identified the limitations of the study as follows, that is, in terms of the longitude effect with which the researcher chose a research issue that did not require excessive time to complete the literature study, use the methodology, collect data, and interpret the results. In addition, in terms of *bias*, the researchers are careful in selecting samples and respondents. Furthermore, in terms of sample size limits which researchers determine so that the sample size is sufficient in qualitative research.

This section deals with the importance of the study. We hope that this study will contribute to the body of educational knowledge in the educational specialization component of secondary education, that is, in the field of creativity and innovative studies. In the context of these learning skills, innovative in teaching and guidance on innovative use in teaching to teachers is important because it has diverse implications. The implication for teachers is that innovative improves the quality of teaching and the effectiveness of teachers. So, this study is expected to contribute to the overall knowledge base on innovative approaches, methods, and techniques of use in teaching. In particular, the study focuses on the practice of creative thinking among teachers and students. Innovative in teaching is significant for teachers' understanding of teaching and learning because it reflects the teacher's core competencies. This study is useful to others in this field, especially in terms of the latest strategies in active learning. Researchers may be able to share the findings of this study with students, teachers, trainee teachers, novice teachers, experienced teachers, expert teachers, lecturers, school inspectorates, curriculum officers, examination officers, administrators, policymakers, parents, and community members.

The purpose of this section is to elaborate the definition for each variable of this study. Researchers identified independent variables, i.e., innovative teaching constraints and dependent variables, i.e., innovative teaching practice.

Innovative Teaching Constraints. In this study, the constraints of innovative teaching refer to some of the teacher's responses to the constraints experienced by teachers such as teachers facing time constraints, routines or task loads, teaching aids, teaching aids, class sizes, and constraints from lack or lack of knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching. Researchers measured it using a structured interview transcript record. Researchers used instruments in the form of Structured Interview Questions by asking teachers to respond to questions such as whether teachers face any constraints or conditions, how constraints or conditions teachers face, and how teachers cope with those constraints or conditions.

Innovative Teaching Skills Practice. In this study, innovative teaching practice among teachers refer to the strategies or tactics of teaching teachers by using various teaching strategies such as query-based teaching, problem-based teaching, teaching using computer technology, and collaborative group teaching. Researchers measured it using a structured interview transcript record. Researchers used instruments in the form of Structured Interview Questions by asking teachers to respond to questions such as whether teachers had ever used one of several

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

innovative teaching strategies, what teaching strategies teachers used, and how teachers used the teaching strategies.

State Government High School Teacher. In this study, State Government Secondary School teachers refer to male teachers and female teachers who are teaching in Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4 in all religious secondary schools of the state government of Selangor, Malaysia.

Literature Review

The Theories that Underlying the Study and Study Theoretical Framework

This section focuses on the theoretical framework of the study. The researcher selects theories related to this area of research. As researchers conducted research on the constraints of innovative teaching and the level of teaching skills of the innovative, the two corresponding theories are the Theory of Constraint by Eliyahu & Jeff (1984) and the Anxiety-Based Adoption Model by Hall & Hord (1987).

Constraint Theory (Eliyahu & Jeff, 1984)

Constraint Theory by Eliyahu & Jeff (1984) suggests that organizations can achieve goals by identifying and leveraging a system of constraints. In terms of identifying constraints, to achieve the goal, the organization must reduce the current congestion. However, organizations can't reduce congestion until the organization knows exactly what it is. In some cases, determining organizational congestion may be easy. The easiest place to start by finding the steps of the organizational process that takes the longest. Technically, constraints are mostly beyond the control of the organization. Then, in terms of exploiting constraints, now that organizations know what organizational constraints are, it's time to exploit that constraint. This step is to ensure that the organization applies constraints to full capacity. Pull organizational constraints and see if there is a clear way that the organization can fix them. Organizational constraints should have the required number of resources from non-constraint to be used optimally.

Next, in terms of increased constraints, now it's time to address the constraints themselves. It can increase the congestion capacity identified by the organization. This will involve upgrading with additional resources. Constraints can include more people, money, and equipment. Finally, in terms of avoiding inertia and repetitive processes, the organization does so in the way it addresses constraints. This means that as soon as the organization corrects one constraint, the organization will definitely find a new one. Organizations should start the process again to identify the next constraint and avoid inertia in the way the organization wants to avoid complacency.

Anxiety-Based Adoption Model (Hall & Hord, 1987)

The Anxiety-Based Adoption Model by Hall & Hord (1987) addresses each assumption about individual concerns about innovative. Moreover, about specific innovative ways of being delivered or implemented, and innovative adaptations to individuals. The principles and concepts of the model explain that change is a process, not an event. It takes time to apply change. Individuals must be in the spotlight if change is facilitated, and the institution will not

change until its members change. The process of change is a very personal experience. Furthermore, how it is perceived by the individual will greatly influence the result. Additionally, individuals progress through various stages regarding their innovative-related emotions and capabilities. Availability of diagnostic or prescriptive models. It can improve individual facilities during staff client-centered development. The party responsible for the change process must work adaptively and systematically, where progress needs to be monitored continuously. In this study, innovative teaching constraints influenced the level of innovative teaching skills among teachers. Researchers explain these relationships and associations as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1
Theoretical Framework of Study

Review-Relevant Past Studies and the Conceptual Framework of Study

This section on the literature review of past studies related to study questions, namely the constraints of innovative teaching among teachers and the practice of innovative teaching skills among teachers.

Constraints of Innovative Teaching Among Teachers

According to David (2019), constraints fall into two categories, namely institutional constraints and the constraints of teachers or educators individually. Institutional constraints are those that have been imposed by the education system and the organizations that finance and supervise the system. These constraints can limit innovative in education. Whereas, the constraint of teachers or educators individually is a constraint in terms of how teachers conduct teaching,

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

whether teachers provide the most effective teaching, what techniques teachers use, and teachers' understanding of educational philosophy.

Neil, Antony, Gavin, & Penny (2020) explore the constraints that control attempts by English teachers to innovate at universities located in the Hinterland area of Southwest China. Their study found that the main constraints included time pressures, competitive priorities, the uproar of new ideas, lack of resources, the superiority of textbooks, and the level of language proficiency among students. According to Amanda, Sandi, & Bernadette (2021), there are five dimensions that serve to curb pedagogical innovations, namely teachers, institutions, colleagues, students, and teaching environments.

Practice of Innovative Teaching Skills Among Teachers

Innovative teaching practices among teachers also refer to the strategies or tactics of teachers to teach by using various teaching strategies such as query-based teaching, problem-based teaching, teaching using computer technology, and group teaching. Practice is implemented as a habit in practice. In this regard, pupils study the practices of others and carry out their activities. It consists of three component forms, namely (1) Planning for practices in which teachers develop learning activities that support pupils in their practice to ensure their actions are focused on successful outcomes, (2) Brief development in which teachers develop learning activities that support pupils to explore what is needed, and (3) Development and evaluation of outcomes for which teachers develop learning activities that support pupils to try, test, and reveal its learning outcomes (New Zealand Ministry of Education, 2020).

To understand the definition of innovative, the OECD identifies and elaborates on four innovative types, namely: (1) Innovative Products: Good introduction or new or significantly improved services in relation to the features or intended use. These include significant improvements in technical specifications, components, and materials, incorporated software, user-friendliness, or other functional features, (2) Innovative Processes: Implementation of new or significant production or delivery methods. These include significant changes in techniques, equipment, and software, (3) Innovative Marketing: Implementation of new marketing methods involving significant changes in product design or packaging, product placement, product promotion, or pricing, and (4) Innovative Organizations: Implementation of new organizational methods in the firm's business practices, workplace organizations or external relations (OECD, 2019).

Therefore, the innovative type associated with teaching is Innovative Process, that is, the implementation of new or tangible methods. These include significant changes in technique and equipment. So, According to Lee (2018), innovative in teaching is design thinking that will help students become more innovative. It involves process, practice, and design thinking teaching 21st-century skills such as expediency, collaboration, and critical thinking. It allows students to use their creativity to address real-world issues. The aim is to achieve better results through the use of five phases of learning, namely empathy, determination, ideas, prototypes, and tests. Murphy, Redding and Twyman (2019) noted that innovative practices can be innovative cultures, in educational organizations or across organizational systems, systematically institutionalizing the following five-phase innovative processes, namely: (1) stimulating innovative to improve learning outcomes; (2) enable potential wearers to choose innovative in accordance with their context and needs; (3) ensure that innovative is implemented with loyalty to the needs of its elements and adaptations to enhance its effectiveness in a given context; (4) facilitate innovative through implementation in multiple

classrooms, schools, and districts; and (5) provide systems to monitor innovative effects and scale, implement the necessary changes.

In this regard, creativity and innovation involve the production of new and worthwhile ideas, as well as filtering ideas that already exist. Creativity and innovation include also being open and responsive to new ideas, and recognizing that these qualities can be enhanced through small successes and frequent mistakes. Creative people use a variety of idea creation techniques, including brainstorming, diagrams, and mind maps. They are interested in trying out original ideas, deciphering, filtering, and working to repair them. Creativity is not just for Art but should be embedded in Mathematics, Science, and History, as well as in all fields (Germaine, Richards, Marilyn, & Cynthia, 2016). In addition, Maslyk (2016) states that there are systematic ways to prepare students for real-world experience. This includes the use of charts, checklists, web links, and profiles to help students connect meaningful subject areas and tap students' curiosity. In summary, the researcher constructs a diagram to clearly determine the construct or variable of the research and its relationship shown by using the arrow as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2
Conceptual Framework of Study

Methodology and Methods

Study Design

This section aims to elaborate the design of this study. In this study, researchers used Qualitative Method Design. Qualitative Method is research in which researchers collect and

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

analyse non-numerical data such as transcripts or interview text to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). In this research, the researchers used Phenomenological Research to investigate two types of phenomena, namely the phenomenon of innovative teaching skills practice and the phenomenon of innovative teaching constraints, by describing and interpreting the life experiences of study participants. It is appropriate to answer two types of questions, which are (1) How is the practice of innovative teaching skills among state government secondary school teachers? (2) How is the constraint of innovative teaching among state government secondary school teachers? This approach becomes the choice of researchers because it is beneficial because this Qualitative Method can be used to gather in-depth insights into the problem or generate new ideas for research. This design prevented the researchers from proceeding with other designs, such as experimental designs, that were not suitable for the variable effects of the study. The form of data collection is to use the Interview Technique through Structured Interview Questions. Researchers administer face-to-face in the field for data security.

Study Variables

In this study, the non-dependent variable was the constraint of innovative teaching among teachers. While the dependent variable is the innovative teaching skills practice among teachers.

Study Instruments

The meaning of this section is to elaborate on the instruments of this study. Researchers used three types of study instruments to obtain data. In this study, researchers used the Teacher Demographic Information Questionnaire, Structured Interview Questions About Innovative Teaching Skills Practice, and Structured Interview Questions About Innovative Teaching Constraints.

Teacher Demographic Information Questionnaire Form. This instrument aims to collect information on respondents who participated in this study. There are three items, namely gender, academic qualifications, and teaching experience.

Structured Interview Questions About Innovative Teaching Skills Practice. The instrument aims to ask teachers to respond to questions such as whether teachers have ever used one of several innovative teaching strategies, what teaching strategies teachers use, and how teachers use the teaching strategy. Then, researchers measured it using a transcript record of this structured interview.

Structured Interview Questions About Innovative Teaching Constraints. This instrument is intended for guidance when the researcher conducts interviews with respondents in terms of the constraints, he faces in applying innovative teaching. The researcher asks the respondent oral questions and records the transcript of the answers. Researchers ask the following questions, namely do teachers face any constraints in innovative teaching, state what the constraints are such as time, task load, teaching aids, teaching aids, class sizes, lack, or lack of knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching, and questions of how teachers cope with constraints.

Validity of the Study

External Validity

In this study, about external validity, there were some of the following assumptions of the study, namely: (i) that the findings of the studies could be applied to the study population, study location, and different study duration despite low ecological validity. This is because the study site was only concentrated in state government secondary schools for only 16 weeks study duration; (ii) that inference can be made to the population based on the findings of this study despite having low population validity because the study participants were not randomly selected independent of the target population, but the study participants were taken from among the teachers who taught in Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4 only.

Internal Validity

In this study, about internal validity, there are several assumptions of the study as follows, namely: (i) that the effect on dependent variables, i.e., innovative teaching skills practice is solely due to independent variables, i.e., constraints on innovative teaching among teachers; (ii) that historical variables did not interfere with the internal validity of the study due to the short duration of the study, which is only 16 weeks.

Reliability of Studies

A pilot study was conducted by researchers to determining the reliability of the Structured Interview Questions. This study has high reliability for the following reason, which is that this study has used a panel of Item Interview Questions Assessors consisting of qualified experts and have been working in the field for a long time.

Study Population

In this study, researchers had a study population of 1129 teachers from 23 State Government Secondary Schools (Department of Islamic Religion, Selangor, 2019).

Study Sampling

In this study, researchers used layered random sampling to select samples among the population. The characteristics of the sample or respondents for qualitative studies are as follows, namely gender, male teachers and female teachers who are teaching in Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4. The respondents of the qualitative study were 25 peoples. A summary of the sample profile of this study is as per Table 1.

Table 1

Summary of Study Sample Profiles

Gender	Number	Per cent
Men	7	28%

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

Female	18	72%
Total	25	100%

Academic Qualifications	Number	Per cent
Graduate	20	80%
Non-Graduate	5	20%
Total	25	100%

Experience	Number	Per cent
10 Years and Under	10	40%
11 Years and Up	15	60%
Total	25	100%

Study Ethics

Researchers adhere to research ethics by following the recommendations of Cresswell & Cresswell (2018). We ensured that the studies used sufficient sample sizes to ensure sufficient strength power. Researchers did not repair or add to the data collected. We did not replicate studies made by other researchers. We also reported conflicting studies. Researchers included the findings despite the negative findings and reported alternative explanations. Researchers shared findings and data with other researchers by publishing studies and not keeping findings in a desk drawer, and when analysing the data, researchers measured control units such as age, gender, and race. Researchers use conceptual or theoretical models as a guide in choosing variables so that all expectations are considered.

Pilot Study

We conducted a pilot study to assess important components of the actual study, namely: (1) Process, i.e. key steps in the actual study are evaluated such as the number of samples and sample criteria, (2) Resources, i.e. assessing problems with time and resources that may occur during the actual study such as how much time it takes the actual study to complete, whether the use of some equipment will be able to implemented or whether the instrument selected for the actual study has reliability or not, (3) Management, that is, problems with data management and with members of the research team involved in actual studies such as problems with collecting all the data necessary for future analysis, whether the data collected is very variable and whether the data from the school different ones can be analysed together. After the interpretation of the results, the researchers concluded that the actual meal can be implemented without changes to the protocol.

Findings/Results

How the Innovative Teaching Strategies Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

The purpose of this section is to elaborate innovative teaching strategies among state government secondary school teachers. Researchers use structured interview techniques to collect qualitative data. Researchers used Themed Approach analysis to track codes or themes about teachers' practices and tactics in innovative teaching based on interview responses. Researchers analysed qualitative data using *N Vivo Version 11* software.

To explain how the innovative teaching strategies among state government secondary school teachers, the researchers carried out the following six steps, namely:

Step 1: Researchers designate a short word or phrase that will be coded as evidence, either to the initial survey or to be used as proof of findings.

Step 2: Researchers get the teacher's response and record how they answer. Researchers rearranged their answers in the form of Table 2.

Table 2

Innovative Teaching Strategies Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

Respondent	Information / Data	Code/Theme
Items Interview	How do you as a teacher use innovative teaching strategies?	
Respondent 1 (R1)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I use a laptop and LCD to display PDPC material, either in the form of pictures or questions. Likewise, I asked students to describe the picture, either individually or in groups. Occasionally, I explain about the display and share other information with students.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondent 2 (R2)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I uploaded real SPM exam questions and SPM Trial exam questions from other states. Furthermore, I use this question in the classroom. Not only that, but I use the OneNote app to store various PDPC materials.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondent 3 (R3)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. Using MS PowerPoint software. I also use Google's Meet app and Microsoft Teams Software to communicate with students.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondent 4 (R4)	I use query-based teaching strategies and teaching strategies in collaboration groups. I made a distribution of assignments and handed	Group Collaborative

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

	over assignments to the students according to the questions listed. As for collaborative group teaching strategies, I share assignments with other fellow teachers and jointly conduct the teaching.	Strategy
Respondent 5 (R5)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I formed a group of students and they made presentations. Students make video recordings as an individual activity.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondent 6 (R6)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I created a group of students and they made presentations. Students conduct learning through games.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondent 7 (R7)	I use query-based teaching strategies. I asked questions related to the content of the lesson to test the students' level of understanding.	Inquiry Strategy
Respondent 8 (R8)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I conducted simulations and case studies.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondent 9 (R9)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I'm running a group discussion session. Likewise, I use Buzz methods, case studies, games, and simulations.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondent 10 (R10)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I created several groups of students and each group completed their respective assignments. Not only that, but I asked each group to present their work.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondent 11 (R11)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I comprised many groups of students and each group completed their respective assignments. Furthermore, I asked each group to present their work and follow a question-and-answer session.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondents 12 (R12)	I use query-based teaching strategies. I conducted a question-and-answer session, encouraging students to answer in the form of statements.	Inquiry Strategy
Respondent 13 (R13)	I use query-based or inquiry-based teaching strategies. I did five phases, which are to question, research, engineer, discuss, and make reflections.	Inquiry Strategy
Respondents 14 (R14)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I'm applying 21st-century teaching.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondents 15 (R15)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I use a computer with an LCD	Computer-Based Strategy

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

	projector to apply listening skills and reading skills.	Strategy
Respondent 16 (R16)	I use query-based or inquiry-based teaching strategies. I made sure that at the beginning, I asked questions to encourage thinking skills among students.	Inquiry Strategy
Respondent 17 (R17)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I created many student groups and each group shared information through the <i>Walking Gallery</i> method. Likewise, I ask if they have a new problem or confusion, they refer to the teacher.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondents 18 (R18)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I give students accurate and easy instructions to solve questions. Likewise, I asked students to make presentations using colourful aids.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondents 19 (R19)	I use teaching strategies using computer technology. I asked students to find their information from the website.	Computer-Based Strategy
Respondents 20 (R20)	I use problem-based teaching strategies. I explain the issue in general. Furthermore, I ask students to use various problem-solving techniques.	Troubleshooting Strategy
Respondent 21 (R21)	I use a query-based teaching strategy, or inquiry. I raise various questions or questions to students to open their minds. Furthermore, I ask students to relate to the content of the lesson and daily life.	Inquiry Strategy
Respondent 22 (R22)	I use problem-based teaching strategies. I give questions to the students and allocate enough time for the students to complete the answers.	Troubleshooting Strategy
Respondents 23 (R23)	I use query-based or inquiry-based teaching strategies. I made sure that at the end of the teaching session, I asked the students questions to test their understanding and I found that there were three groups of students, who were weak, moderate, and excellent.	Inquiry Strategy
Respondents 24 (R24)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I give instructions concisely and accurately to all groups. Furthermore, I asked students to make presentations using various aids.	Group Collaborative Strategy
Respondents 25 (R25)	I use a collaborative group teaching strategy. I give instructions concisely and accurately to all groups. Likewise, I asked each group to make a presentation, followed by a question-and-answer session.	Group Collaborative Strategy

Figure 4
Information By Category Based on Hierarchy

use	students	respondent	asked	strategy	assignment	session	answer	give	informa	inquiry	present			
					furthermor	problem	accur	aids	lamon	app	case	comp	concis	
		strategies	based	collaborative	groups	likewise	various	condu	expla	form	game	innova	cd	lesson
						condu	many	simul	softwa	spm	studies	sure		
	teaching	group	questions	computer	technology	made	ask	contep	dp	teach	work	21sacc	dact	allc
						make	created	displa	prese	teach	also	buz	cen	clasc
		using	respondents	query	instructi	either	respe	test	appl	com	desc	distre	easy	
					question	skills	exam	share	under	appl	com	discu	encd	end
										begi	com	discu	encd	engit

Step 6: The researchers perform the analysis through the interpretation of the data with the advice of expertise. The findings of individually structured interviews show that teachers adopt innovative teaching strategies through computer technology-based teaching and collaborative groups. The findings showed that teachers adopt innovative teaching strategies through question-based teaching and problem-solving.

How to Constrain Innovative Teaching Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

The purpose of this section is to explain how to constrain innovative teaching among state government secondary school teachers. Researchers use structured interview techniques to collect qualitative data. Researchers used Themed Approach analysis to detect code or themes about constraints in innovative teaching based on interview responses. Researchers analysed qualitative data using *N vivo Version 11* software.

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

To explain how constrained innovative teaching is among state government high school teachers, the researchers carried out the following six steps, namely:

Step 1: Researchers designate a short word or phrase that will be coded as evidence, either to the initial survey or to be used as proof of findings.

Step 2: Researchers get the teacher's response and record how they answer. Researchers rearranged their answers in the form of Table 3.

Table 3
Innovative Teaching Constraints Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

Respondent	Information / Data	Code/Theme
Items Interview	As a teacher, what constraints or obstacles do you face in the use of innovative teaching?	
Respondent 1 (R1)	I have many workloads apart from PDPC. I also do other work like making reports and documentation. Furthermore, I had a solid time with the school programs. Moreover, I'm also not good enough at ICT use.	Task Load Constraint Time constraints Skills constraints ICT
Respondent 2 (R2)	I have started using laptops for PDPC. However, I am still not good at using many applications. I have a hard time understanding the instructions.	Skills constraints ICT
Respondent 3 (R3)	I don't have any aids because I can't afford complete ICT equipment. I also lack the knowledge to handle ICT equipment.	ICT Knowledge Constraint
Respondent 4 (R4)	I use ICT if there is time and there is good Internet access. I will use ICT if I have the opportunity.	Internet Access Constraints
Respondent 5 (R5)	I lack knowledge of ICT because I am more than 50 years old.	ICT Knowledge Constraint
Respondent 6 (R6)	I did not master the knowledge in the use of new applications for PDPC.	ICT Knowledge Constraint
Respondent 7 (R7)	I don't have any constraints or obstacles.	
Respondent 8 (R8)	I lack knowledge of ICT and have less time to use ICT equipment.	ICT Knowledge Constraint Time constraints
Respondent 9 (R9)	I did not face any obstacles or constraints.	
Respondent 10 (R10)	I have other workloads in addition to PDPC duties. I also have many students and a solid timetable.	Task Load Constraint

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

Respondent 11 (R11)	I have many students in the classroom.	Number of Students Constraint
Respondents 12 (R12)	I'm not good at innovative teaching.	Skills constraints ICT Skills constraints ICT
Respondent 13 (R13)	I have a big issue due to poor Internet access in residential areas. It took me a lot of time to share learning materials with students.	Internet Access Constraints
Respondents 14 (R14)	I have a burdensome clerical job. Internet facilities in schools are limited. I installed my teaching aids, causing there to be time constraints.	Task Load Constraint
Respondents 15 (R15)	I have an issue of lack of ICT equipment and auxiliary materials in the classroom.	Equipment Deficiency Constraint
Respondent 16 (R16)	I have the issue of lack of ICT equipment such as LCD projector for in-class teaching sessions.	Equipment Deficiency Constraint
Respondent 17 (R17)	I used to go out of school to do other tasks outside.	Time constraints
Respondents 18 (R18)	I have a heavy workload. I'm weak in time management. Likewise, I lack knowledge of ICT.	Task Load Constraint
Respondents 19 (R19)	I have the issue of lack of ICT equipment such as LCD projector for in-class teaching sessions. I had to share the use of ICT equipment with other teachers.	Equipment Deficiency Constraint
Respondents 20 (R20)	I have constraints to choose the right location for PDPC apart from using classrooms.	
Respondent 21 (R21)	I have the constraints to get a reference book in the field of teaching. I'm not good at global PDPC methods.	Skills constraints ICT
Respondent 22 (R22)	I have many students in the classroom. I am faced with the issue of students who are not interested in the subjects I teach. Likewise, I have constraints in terms of teaching and learning equipment.	Number of Students Constraint
Respondents 23 (R23)	I'm less adept at leading classes because I'm less assertive. I'm less proficient in the use of 21st-century teaching. Likewise, I don't know how to use voice intonation well.	Skills constraints ICT
Respondents 24	I have a heavy workload. I'm not competent in time management. Furthermore, I lack knowledge of ICT.	Task Load Constraint

The study found that teachers faced constraint in terms of time, routine or task load, teaching aids, teaching aids, class sizes, and constraints from lack or lack of knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching. The findings show that teachers face crackdown in the use of innovative teaching. The findings showed that teachers are less proficient in using Information and Communication Technology (ICT), teachers teach classes where many students are, and teachers face constraints in terms of time, equipment, task load, and Internet speed. It is in line with the findings of the Neil, Antony, Gavin, & Penny (2020) study which found that the main constraints include time pressures, competitive priorities, the advent of new ideas, lack of resources, the superiority of textbooks, and the level of language proficiency among teachers. This finding is also supported by Amanda, Sandi, & Bernadette (2021) who states that there are five dimensions that serve to curb pedagogical innovations, namely teachers, institutions, colleagues, students, and the teaching environment.

Recommendations

The purpose of this section is to submit recommendations. In this regard, researchers suggest that school inspectorate, curriculum officers, examination officers, administrators, policymakers, parents, and community members solve the issue of teachers facing constraint in terms of time, routine or task load, teaching aids, teaching aids, class sizes, and constraints from lack or lack of knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching. In addition, the researchers also recommend further research on this topic at the university, college, and primary school level.

Conclusions

The main findings show that teachers adopt innovative teaching strategies through computer technology-based teaching and collaborative groups. Furthermore, teachers adopt innovative teaching strategies through question-based teaching and problem-solving. Addition, teachers face crackdown in the use of innovative teaching. Further, teachers are less proficient in using Information and Communication Technology (ICT), teachers teach classes where many students are, and teachers face constraints in terms of time, equipment, task load, and Internet speed.

This section deals with the implications of this study. The main findings of this study show that teachers adopt innovative teaching strategies through computer technology-based teaching and collaborative groups. The findings showed that teachers adopt innovative teaching strategies through question-based teaching and problem-solving. It also has implications for the practice of teachers, trainee teachers, novice teachers, experienced teachers, expert teachers, and lecturers. This study indicates that teachers face limitations in terms of time, routine or task load, teaching aids, teaching aids, class sizes, and constraints from lack or lack of knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching. It has implications for the practices of teachers, lecturers, school inspectorate, curriculum officers, exam officers, administrators, policymakers, parents, and community members. The findings of this study in theoretical and

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

policy terms contribute to the body of educational knowledge in the component of educational specialization for secondary education, that is, in the field of creativity and innovative studies.

In relation to the limitations of this study in terms of the main objective of the research, this refers to the concept that is the focus of this study alone, which is the practice of innovative teaching skills among teachers and the constraints of innovative teaching among teachers. Moreover, the limitations of this study in terms of independent variables and dependent variables, this refers to the variables that are the focus of this study alone, i.e., the independent variables in this study are the constraints of innovative teaching among teachers. While the variable leaning on this study is the practice of innovative teaching skills. Independent variables affect the dependent variable. Then, the limitations of this study in terms of the subject or participants of the study, this refers to the respondents or participants of this study only. The subjects of this study are male teachers and female teachers who are teaching in Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4 in all state religious secondary schools. In addition, the limitations of this study in terms of the duration of the research time and the location of the study, this refers to the duration of the research time and the location of the study alone. The study took a 16-week dive period. The location of this study was in secondary schools of the state government of Selangor, Malaysia.

References

- Amanda, G., Sandi, T. M., & Bernadette, K. (2021) Innovative teaching in higher education: Teachers' perceptions of support and constraint, *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 58(2), 123-134, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2020.1715816>
- Creswell, J. W. & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design*. SAGE Publication.
- David, M. S. (2019). Constraints on innovative teaching in British universities: an American perspective, *Journal of Scholarly Teaching*, 14, 88-98. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1222828.pdf>
- Department of Islamic Religion. (2019). *Teacher statistic*. Selangor, Malaysia.
- Eliyahu, G. M. & Jeff, C (1984). *The goal: A process of ongoing improvement*. National Productivity Institute.
- Guerriero, S. and Révai, N. (2017.) Knowledge-based teaching and the evolution of a profession. In: Guerriero S (ed) *Pedagogical Knowledge and the Changing Nature of the Teaching Profession*. OECD Publishing.
- Germaine, R., Richards, J., Koeller, M., Cynthia, S. (2016). Purposeful use of 21st century skills in higher education. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching*, 9(1), 19 – 29. <https://assets.nu.edu/assets/resources/pageResources/journal-of-research-in-innovative-teaching-volume-9.pdf>
- Hall, G.E. & Hord, S.M., (1987). *Change in schools: Facilitating the process*. State University of New York Press.
- Karen, C. (2016, July 26). Creating classroom experiences that grab and hold students' interest is not only good teaching, it's good science. <https://www.insidehighered.com/advice/2016/07/26/how-hold-students-attention-classroom-essay>
- Kathryn, P. H. (2016, Feb 15). This is what happens when kids' creative strengths are leveraged. <http://www.creativitypost.com/education/this-is-what-happens-when-kids-creative>
- Lee, D. (2018). *Design thinking in the classroom: Easy-to-use teaching tools to foster creativity, encourage innovation, and unleash potential in every student*. Ulysses Press.
- Lund, T. C. & Grams, D. (2017). *Innovative pedagogy*. Creative Education Book series. BrillSense.
- Maslyk, J. (2016). *STEAM makers: Fostering creativity and innovation in the elementary classroom*. 1st Edition. Corwin.

Abu Bakar Mohd Sheikh, Mohd Nothman Mohamad Nor & Constraints and Innovative Teaching Skills Practice Among State Government Secondary School Teachers

Murphy, M., Sam, R., & Twyman, S. (Eds). (2019). *Handbook on Personalized Learning for States, Districts, and Schools*. Center on Innovations in Learning. Temple University.

Neil, M., Antony, J. L., Gavin, Z., & Penny, M. (2020). Constraints on innovation in English language teaching in Hinterland Regions of China, *Language Teaching Research*, December, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820979855>

New Zealand Ministry of Education. (2020). Technological practice. TKI. <https://technology.tki.org.nz/Technology-in-the-NZC/Technological-practice>

Stéphan, V., Joaquin, U., Soumyajit, K., and Gwénaél, J. (2019). Measuring innovation in education: What has changed in the classroom? *Educational Research and Innovation*, OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264311671-en>